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SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF PHENYLEPHRINE HYDROCHLORIDE AND KETOROLAC TROMETHAMINE USING UV SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC AND HPLC METHODS

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ABSTRACT

This study involve development of a simple, sensitive, precise, accurate and economic HPLC method and two UV methods for simultaneous estimation of phenylephrine HCl (Phe) and ketorolac tromethamine (Ket). The UV methods are based upon absorption correction and multicomponent analysis approach. Wavelength maxima (λ_{max}) selected for Phe and Ket were 273 nm and 323 nm respectively. Selected linearity ranges for Phe and Ket were 12-42 ppm and 4-14 ppm respectively for UV methods. HPLC method was developed using Waters HILIC (Hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography) column having dimension of 150 mm x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m. Mobile phase used was acetate buffer (pH 3.2; 10mM): MeOH: ACN:: 32:23:45 with flow rate of 1mL/min at detection wavelength of 275nm. Retention time for Phe and Ket were 2.96 and 1.96 min. Linearity ranges for Phe and Ket chosen were 30-60 and 10-20 μ g/mL respectively for HPLC method. Thus, selective and robust spectrophotometric and chromatographic methods were developed successfully and also validated for various parameters like accuracy, precision (intra-day and inter-day), linearity and range, limit of detection and limit of quantitation (LOD and LOQ) as per ICH guidelines. % Assay was also determined and found to be in accordance with the label claim. Both the developed methods are quite sensitive for simultaneous identification and analysis of Phe and Ket in bulk.

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INTRODUCTION

Chemically, Ketorolac (Ket) is (-)-5-Benzoyl-1,2-dihydro-3H-pyrrolo[1,2-a] pyrrole-1-carboxylic acid (Figure 1 A). It is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory agent with potent analgesic activity. Usually it is administered orally as its tromethamine salt having potent cyclooxygenase inhibitory activity therefore used as analgesic and anti-inflammatory moiety. Available clinical data indicates that a single dose of Ket is as effective as of aspirin and paracetamol and much more effective than that of morphine and pethidine [1].

Chemically, phenylephrine HCl (Phe) is (R)-1-(3-hydroxy phenyl)-2-methylamino ethanol hydrochloride (Figure 1 B). It is alpha-1 adrenoreceptor agonist and used as a decongestant [2].

OMIDRIA[®] a fixed dose combination of Ket and Phe is used as mydriatic agent *i.e.* eye irrigating solution during cataract surgery [3].

Figure-1: Structure of (A) Ketorolac Tromethamine (Ket); (B) Phenylephrine HCl (Phe).

In this study, two UV methods were developed for simultaneous estimation of Phe and Ket. Absorption correction method is used if the sample contains two absorbing drugs (X and Y), one of which (X) absorbs at the λ_{\max} of other (Y) but other (Y) shows zero absorbance at λ_{\max} of first (X) then, it may be possible to determine both the drug by simplified simultaneous equation method using following formula [4].

$$A_1 = a_{X1} \cdot C_x + a_{Y1} \cdot C_y$$

$$A_2 = a_{X2} \cdot C_x + a_{Y2} \cdot C_y$$

Where, A_1 and A_2 = Absorbances of the mixture at λ_1 and λ_2 respectively; a_{X1} = absorptivity of X at λ_1 nm; a_{X2} = absorptivity of X at λ_2 nm; a_{Y1} = absorptivity of Y at λ_1 nm; a_{Y2} = absorptivity of Y at λ_2 nm; C_x = concentration of X; C_y = concentration of Y.

In multi component analysis approach, the concentration of each constituent is determined using absorption spectra of the mixed sample with pure standards. It is the most sensitive and accurate measurement technique for simultaneous estimation of drugs. Spectral data are promptly acquired with ease and also time consuming prior separation procedures including extraction, concentration of constituents and the clean-up steps can be avoided [5].

Various spectrophotometric and chromatographic analytical methods are available for determination of both the drugs individual [6-25]. Prava, V. and Seru G. have also reported HPLC method for both the drugs simultaneously [26]. But simultaneous estimation of Phe and Ket using absorbance correction and multicomponent quantitation UV methods; and by HPLC method using HILIC column have not yet been reported. Thus, the main objective to carry out present study is to develop a simple, accurate, precise, specific, sensitive and robust UV spectrophotometric and HPLC methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and reagents:

Phe and Ket reference standards were purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Bengaluru, India. Because of the unavailability of the marketed formulation OMIDRIA[®] in a local market, a laboratory mixture of Phe and Ket was prepared in proportion of 3:1. Methanol (MeOH) and acetonitrile (ACN) of analytical grade and HPLC grade were obtained from Spectrochem Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai India. Other reagents like ammonium acetate buffer and acetic acid were procured from Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. All the solutions were prepared in HPLC grade water and filtered through 0.2 μ millipore membrane filter before injecting into HPLC.

Instrumentation:

UV spectrophotometer:

Simultaneous spectrophotometric estimation of Phe and Ket were carried out using Shimadzu UV-1700 double beam spectrophotometer equipped with Shimadzu UV Probe 2.10 software. Matched quartz cuvettes of 1 cm was utilized to hold drug solution to be analyzed and UV spectrum was recorded over range of 200-400 nm.

HPLC

A simultaneous chromatographic evaluation of Phe and Ket in both bulk and laboratory mixture was performed on Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan equipped with LC-20AT pump, Rheodyne 7725 injector with loop capacity of 20 μ L and Shimadzu SPD-20AV detector. HPLC column used was HILIC column (150mm x 4.6mm, 5 μ m).

Preparation of stock solution and working solution (Common for UV and HPLC method):

Accurately weighed 10 mg of Phe and Ket were individually transferred to 10 mL volumetric flasks and diluted with MeOH to get stock solutions of two drugs having 1000 μ g/mL concentration. Working solutions of Phe and Ket both having 100 μ g/mL concentration were prepared from stock solutions by withdrawing 1mL respectively from each and volume was made upto the mark in a 10 mL volumetric flask using the same diluent.

Preparation of calibration standards of Phe and Ket

UV methods I and II:

From working solutions of 100 μ g/mL of Phe and Ket, aliquots of 1.2 mL and 0.4 mL respectively were withdrawn, and mixed in 10 mL volumetric flasks and diluted upto the mark with mobile phase. Same procedure was followed for other aliquots of 1.8, 2.4, 3.0, 3.6, 4.2 mL and of 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4 mL of Phe and Ket respectively. Thus final solutions containing Phe and Ket in the ratio of 3:1 were analyzed by UV spectrophotometer at two different wavelength i.e. at 273 nm and 323 nm.

HPLC method:

From working solutions of 100 μ g/mL of Phe and Ket, aliquots of 3.0 mL and 1.0 mL respectively were withdrawn, and mixed in 10 mL volumetric flasks and diluted upto the mark with mobile phase. Same procedure was followed for other aliquots of 3.0, 3.6, 4.2, 4.8, 5.4, 6.0 mL and of 1.0, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6, 1.8, 2.0 mL of Phe and Ket respectively. Thus final solutions containing Phe and Ket in the ratio of 3:1 were analyzed by HPLC.

Selection of common analytical wavelength for both APIs:

Solutions of Phe and Ket were scanned using UV spectrophotometer in range of 200-400 nm. Overlain spectra individually of both drug were used for selection of analytical wavelength and 275 nm was selected as analytical wavelength as shown in Figure 2.

Figure-2: Common Wavelength Selection for Phe (Pink) and Ket (Blue) by UV Spectrophotometry.

Chromatographic procedure:

HPLC analysis was performed using Waters HILIC column. Different ratio of MeOH, ACN and acetate buffer at the different flow rates (0.9, 1.0 and 1.1 mL/min), different buffer pH (3.2, 3.5 and 4.2) at detection wavelength of 275 nm were tried. Finally the method was optimized and developed using a ratio 32:23:37 of acetate buffer (pH:3.2, 10mM, 0.05% TEA, filtered through 0.2 μ millipore membrane filter):MeOH:ACN respectively at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min and detection wavelength of 275 nm as it showed symmetric chromatographic peaks for both Phe and Ket within system suitability parameters (table 1).

Table-1. Optimized chromatographic conditions for Phe and Ket.

METHOD PARAMETER	OPTIMIZED VALUE
Column	Waters HILIC (150 mm x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase	Acetate buffer (pH 3.2):MeOH:ACN::32:23:45
Flow rate	1.0 mL/min
Retention Time	1.96 min for Ket and 2.96 min for Phe
Detection Wavelength	275 nm

Validation of developed UV method and HPLC method:

Developed UV methods were validated for various parameters like accuracy (%recovery), intra-day and inter-day precision, linearity and range, LOD (limit of detection) and LOQ (limit of quantitation), robustness according to ICH Q2(R1) guideline. For HPLC method, besides this parameters, system suitability parameters were also measured.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Developed and optimized UV spectrophotometric and chromatographic methods were validated for various parameters discussed in following sections.

Linearity and Range:

Linearity solutions ranging from concentration of 12-42 and 4-14 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (for UV methods) and 30-60 and 10-20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (for HPLC method) for Phe and Ket respectively were prepared and analyzed in triplicate at a constant injection volume of 10 μL . Calibration curve and r^2 value for UV methods (Figure 3) and HPLC method were generated (Figure 4). UV spectra and HPLC chromatogram for linearity is depicted in figure 5 and 6 respectively (Table 2 and 3).

Figure 3(a)

Figure 3(b)

Figure 3(c)

Figure 3(d)

Figure-3: Calibration Curve For (A) Phe and (B) Ket by Absorbance Correction Method, (C) Phe And (D) Ket by Multi-Component Analysis Method.

Table-2: Validation parameters results for UV methods:

Parameter	Absorbance Correction Method		Multi-component Analysis Method	
	Phenylephrine HCl	Ketorolac Tromethamine	Phenylephrine HCl	Ketorolac Tromethamine
Analytical wavelength(nm)	273nm	323.5nm	273nm	323.5nm
Linearity range($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	12-42 ppm	4-14ppm	12-42 ppm	4-14ppm
Regression Equation	$y = 0.008x + 0.005$	$y = 0.05x + 0.049$	$y = 1.000x - 0.242$	$y = 1.011x - 0.440$
Correlation coefficient	0.997	0.996	0.998	0.999
LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	1.386	1.59	0.737	0.666
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	4.05	4.85	2.23	2.01
Intra-day precision (%RSD)	0.789	1.0082	1.082	1.349
Inter-day precision (%RSD)	1.02	1.0037	1.235	1.426

Table-3: Validation parameters results for RP-HPLC method:

Parameter	HPLC method	
	Phenylephrine HCl	Ketorolac Tromethamine
Common Analytical wavelength(nm) for both APIs	275 nm	275 nm
Linearity range($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	30-60 ppm	10-20 ppm
Regression Equation	$y = 8.4755x - 125.52$	$y = 8.1165x - 31.528$
Correlation coefficient	0.9965	0.9977
LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.4737	0.565
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	1.435	1.712
Intra-day precision (%RSD)	0.387	1.055
Inter-day precision (%RSD)	0.714	1.243

(a)

(b)

Figure-4: Calibration Curve of (A) Phe (12-42 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) and Ket (4-14 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) by HPLC method.**LOD and LOQ (Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantitation)**

LOD and LOQ of both UV and HPLC methods were determined using standard deviation of response and slope of calibration curve approach. Six replicates of the drug sample with lowest detectable and quantifiable concentration were injected and %RSD was determined (Table 2 and 3).

Figure-5: Calibration Curve for Phe and Ket using UV Method.

Figure-6: Calibration Curve for Phe and Ket using HPLC Method.

Precision (Intra-day Precision and Inter-day Precision):

Precision was calculated by analysing LQC (low quality control), MQC (medium quality control) and HQC (high quality control) in six replicates on same day (intra-day) and at different days (inter-day). Standard deviation (SD) and relative standard deviation (%RSD) were calculated (Table 2 and 3).

Accuracy (%Recovery):

Standard addition method was applied to express accuracy of method to drug sample by spiking known amount of Ket and Phe corresponding 80, 100, and 120% *i.e.* 9.92, 12.4 and 14.88 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for Phe and 3.39, 4.24 and 5.08 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for Ket to fixed concentration of its laboratory mixture. %Recovery and SD were designed as depicted table 4.

Table-4: Results of Accuracy for UV and HPLC method.

% spiking	% Recovery* \pm					
	Standard Deviation					
	Absorbance Correction Method		Multi-component Method		RP-HPLC method	
	Phe	Ket	Phe	Ket	Phe	Ket
80	98.7 \pm 0.787	99.52 \pm 0.632	100.32 \pm 0.348	98.58 \pm 0.556	98.79 \pm 0.220	97.34 \pm 0.858
100	99.67 \pm 0.536	100.23 \pm 0.476	99.43 \pm 0.186	100.47 \pm 0.361	99.19 \pm 0.248	98.58 \pm 0.742
120	100.26 \pm 0.473	99.68 \pm 0.843	99.78 \pm 0.214	98.89 \pm 0.486	98.79 \pm 0.232	99.09 \pm 0.912

%Assay:

%Assay was determined by analysing similar concentration of Phe and Ket solution and laboratory mixture in UV and HPLC. The value of % assay was calculated by comparing absorbance (for UV methods) and area of chromatographic peak (for HPLC method) of laboratory mixture with drug standard and their results are listed in Table 5.

Table-5: % assay of synthetic mixture of Phe and Ket.

APIs	Labelled Claim	% Assay by Absorption Correction method	% Assay by Multi-component Quantitation Mode	% Assay by RP-HPLC method
Phe	12.42 mg	99.54±0.280	99.81± 1.010	98.92± 0.230
Ket	4.24 mg	99.84±1.41	99.31±0.147309	98.31 ± 0.867

Specificity

Specificity of the method was demonstrated by injecting the blank solution, standard solution and sample solution prepared from laboratory mixture with excipient and responses were determined. There was no interfering peak of any excipient in the chromatogram.

Robustness

Robustness of the method was demonstrated by deliberately changing the chromatographic conditions like pH, grade of acetonitrile used and flow rate (table 6).

Table-6: Robustness results for both the method.

Chromatographic Condition	Range	Chromatographic Parameters			
		Retention time (min)		Peak Area (mV.sec)	
		Phe	Ket	Phe	Ket
pH (Unit)	3.1	2.54	1.92	363.21	146.54
	3.3	2.56	1.97	363.32	147.12
	3.5	2.57	1.96	363.52	146.80
Flow Rate (mL/min)	0.9	2.6	2.1	360.52	149.53
	1.0	2.56	1.96	362.12	148.23
	1.1	2.5	1.86	364.23	147.52
Buffer Ratio (%)	30:70	2.65	1.8	360.52	147.58
	32:68	2.54	1.96	362.12	146.23
	34:66	2.39	2.01	364.23	148.52

System Suitability Parameters for HPLC method:

System suitability test was carried out on freshly prepared standard solutions containing Phe and Ket. System suitability parameters obtained with 20 µL injection volumes are summarized below table 7.

Table-7: System Suitability Parameters for Phe and Ket.

Parameters	Data Obtained*	
	Phe	Ket
Retention time ± SD	2.56±0.123	1.96 ± 0.075
Theoretical plate ± SD	2245 ± 12.56	2100 ± 32.563
Tailing factor ± SD	1.52 ± 0.089	1.79±0.0356
Resolution ± SD	2.5±0.0789	-

*Data shown is the average of six replicates. SD= Standard Deviation.

Stability in sample solutions:

Working solution of Phe and Ket prepared from standard stock solution were kept at room temperature for 24 hrs and then they were analysed by developed and optimized UV and HPLC methods. Absence of extra peak confirmed stability of both the drugs at room temperature.

CONCLUSION

The developed UV and HPLC methods for simultaneous estimation of phenylephrine HCl and ketorolac tromethamine were sensitive, robust and rapid. Both methods were successfully validated according to ICH Q2 (R1) guidelines. %Assay values obtained by UV and HPLC method were within the limit specified by ICH Q2 (R1) guideline. Developed HPLC method is advantageous over literature in terms of reduction in chromatographic run time which gave a cheapest HPLC method due to lesser consumption of organic solvents which in turn reduce in analysis time. Developed method can be implemented for detection of Phe and Ket in biological matrices in future.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

The authors declare no conflict of interest

ABBREVIATIONS

Phe	: Phenylephrine hydrochloride
Ket	: Ketorolac tromethamine
LOD	: Limit of detection
LOQ	: Limit of quantitation
HPLC	: High performance liquid chromatography
UV	: Ultraviolet
MeOH	: Methanol
CAN	: Acetonitrile
TEA	: Tetraethylamine
ICH	: International Conference on harmonization
%RSD	: % Relative standard deviation

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